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Abstracts

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FunGlass

Micro and nano-sized glass particles for biomedical applications

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Abstract

Preparation of glass particles of suitable morphology (size, shape) and surface properties, such as surface area, roughness, surface charge, and topography, are of primary importance for a range of biomedical applications. These properties influence the ability of such particles to be used for direct use in human body, e.g. for targeted “on-site” treatment, and controlled release of drugs and therapeutic ions, or their further use in more complex structures, such as 3D scaffolds or bioactive glass containing composites with biopolymer matrix for hard and soft tissue regeneration. In addition, surface properties, together with overall chemical composition define, to a large extent, also the kinetic of dissolution of glass particles, and hence, release of therapeutic ions from glass structure. The presentation summarises our efforts in preparation of micro- and nanometer-sized glass particles with various morphology and composition aimed for biomedical applications. These include the application of flame synthesis for preparation of (i) bioinert yttrium-aluminate hollow glass microspheres designed for local radiotherapy, (ii) solid and porous bioactive glass microspheres of various compositions for preparation of 3D glass scaffolds by additive manufacturing technologies or stacking of glass tapes prepared by tape casting, (iii) Co and B-doped angiogenesis promoting solid nanoparticles up to 300 nm in size applicable also as filler into biopolymer matrices, and finally (iv) sol-gel derived mesoporous nanoparticles for drug delivery doped with various therapeutic ions.